

applied for selective demethylation of the 5-OCH₃ group of flavones.

On refluxing with 6 *N* ethanolic HCl for 10 h, **2** underwent complete demethylation producing **4**, while under identical condition **1** was only slightly (~5%) demethylated. When an ethereal solution of **2** was treated with dry AlCl₃, it was completely demethylated within 48 h¹, but under the same condition **1** remained mainly (~90%) unconverted. On increasing the time of the AlCl₃-induced reaction to 7 days, **1** was found to undergo about 30% demethylation. This difference in the reactivities of **1** and **2** may also be ascribed to their difference in the sites of fusion of the furano moiety to the flavone nucleus.

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Chemical Investigation of the Aerial Parts of Different *Clerodendron* Species

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IN pursuing our interest¹ in terpenoid constituents of the *Clerodendron* genus (Verbenaceae), we have examined *Clerodendron splendens* Don., an ornamental climbing shrub having red flowers, and *Cleroden-*

dron neutens Wall., a bushy shrub. The plants were collected from the Taj Garden, Agra, and carefully identified by the Horticulture Department. A perusal of literature reveal that no work has been reported on any part of *Clerodendron splendens* and *Clerodendron neutens*. Chemical investigation of their aerial parts was, therefore, undertaken and the results are summarised in this communication.

The light-petroleum extract of the aerial parts of the *C. splendens* afforded Clerodolone, (24s)ethylcholesta-5,22,25-triene-3 β -ol, n-triacontane, friedelan-3 β -ol, friedelan-3-one and β -amyrin; while clerosterol, clerodolone, (24s)ethylcholesta-5,22,25-triene-3 β -ol, β -sitosterol and stigmasterol have been isolated from the light-petroleum extract of the *C. neutens*.

Experimental

Completely air-dried and coarsely powdered aerial parts of *C. splendens* (3.0 kg) and *C. neutens* (3.0 kg) were repeatedly extracted with light-petroleum (b.p. 60-80) on steam-bath for 3 \times 12 h separately. The extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure and the resulting brownish mass was chromatographed over 60-120 mesh silica-gel (350 g) using a borosil glass column of size 3' \times 2.5" separately.

Chromatographic fractions were collected in the following order in *C. splendens*: Fraction 1 (petrol), Fraction 2 (petrol-C₆H₆, 1:1), Fraction 3 (C₆H₆), Fraction 4 (C₆H₆-CH₂COOC₂H₅, 9:1), Fraction 5 (C₆H₆-CH₂COOC₂H₅, 1:1), Fraction 6 (CH₂-COOC₂H₅) and Fraction 7 (CH₂COOC₂H₅-MeOH, 9:1). Purity of each fraction was checked on tlc plate (silica-gel) using various solvent mixtures as eluents and the following compounds were obtained in pure state after repeated crystallisation. The identity of the compounds were confirmed by spectral (ir, ¹H nmr, mass) and chemical studies as well as by co-tlc with authentic samples. The spots on tlc plates were visualised using 1% ceric sulphate in 2 *N* H₂SO₄ as spray reagent.

(24s)Ethylcholesta-5,22,25-triene-3 β -ol: Yellowish white solid (100 mg) was obtained after removal of the solvent from light-petrol and benzene (1:1) fraction. Crystallisation from light petrol gave colourless needles, m.p. 144-45°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3450-3230 (OH), 1640 and 800 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃) 0.7 (3H, s), 0.95 (3H, s), 1.00 (3H, d), 1.65 (3H, brs), 0.83 (3H, t), 4.68 (1H, dd), 3.5 (1H, m), 5.22 (1H, dd), 5.3 (2H, m), *M*⁺, 410, C₂₉H₄₆O; acetate (Ac₂O/Py), m.p. 140°^a.

Friedelan-3-one: Benzene fraction on repeated crystallisation gave colourless needles (150 mg), m.p. 258-59°; gave positive Liebermann-Burchard and Noller's tests⁸; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1720 (C=O), 2950 and 2885 cm⁻¹, *M*⁺, 426, C₃₀H₅₀O. This was converted to friedelan-3 β -ol by sodium borohydride reduction, which was identical with the natural product.

Friedelan-3 β -ol: White solid (150 mg) obtained from benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) fraction on crystallisation gave shining flakes, m.p. 276°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3480 (OH), 1450, 1360 and 1050 cm^{-1} ; M^+ , 428, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}$; acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$), m.p. 290-291° (lit.⁴, 292-294°); identified as friedelan-3 β -ol by comparing with an authentic sample.

Clerodolone: Methanolic extract of each plant gave clerodolone, as white granules on cooling. Repeated crystallisation with methanol gave colourless needles (50 mg), m.p. 288-89°; gave positive Liebermann-Burchard and INM tests indicating unsaturated nature; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3550 (OH), 1690, 1645 and 860 cm^{-1} ; M^+ , 456; confirmed by comparing with an authentic sample.

n-Triacontane and β -amyrin were also identified by comparing with an authentic sample.

Chromatographic fractionation of the aerial parts of the *C. neutens* afforded the following compounds. Fraction 1 (petrol- C_6H_6 , 1:1) afforded (24s)ethylcholesta-5,22,25-triene-3 β -ol; while β -sitosterol was obtained from the C_6H_6 fraction. Stigmasterol was collected from Fraction 4 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_6 - \text{CH}_3\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$, 9:1), and Fraction 5 ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_6 - \text{CH}_3\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$, 1:1) gave clerosterol.

Clerosterol: White solid (100 mg) obtained from the benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1) fraction on crystallisation yielded white needles, m.p. 146-47°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3450-3230 (OH), 1640, 960 and 890 cm^{-1} ; M^+ , 412, $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}_2$; responded to TNM and Liebermann-Burchard colour tests; acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$), m.p. 140° (lit.⁶, m.p. 142°).

β -Sitosterol and stigmasterol were identified by comparing with an authentic sample.

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Biflavones from *Juniperus indica* (Syn. *J. pseudosabina*)

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A number of *Juniperus* species¹⁻⁷ have been examined for biflavonoids but no work has been reported so far on *Juniperus indica* (Syn. *J. Pseudosabina*). The plant leaves were chemically examined and found to contain six biflavones, two of them being minor could only be detected.

Experimental

Acetone extracts of dry leaves (3 kg) collected from Royal Botanical Garden, Godawari, Lalitpur, Nepal, after the usual purification by solvent treatment and column chromatography (Si-gel) were separated into three flavonoid fractions, I (Rf 0.16), II (Rf 0.37) and III (Rf 0.54) by preparative tlc (benzene-pyridine-formic acid, 36:9:5). Fraction I was found to be the mixture of two biflavones (tlc of the methylated product). It was subjected to CCD separation between MeCOEt and borate buffer (pH 9.8) which yielded compounds A and B. These were characterised as amentoflavone and cupressuflavone, respectively by comparison of m.p., m. m.p., chromatographic and pmr data of their methyl ethers and acetates with those of authentic samples^{8,9}. Fraction II on methylation ($\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{K}_2\text{SO}_3$) gave three methyl ethers on tlc, corresponding to amentoflavone and cupressuflavone hexamethyl ethers and hinokiflavone pentamethyl ether (Rf and shade in uv light)¹⁰. Fraction II was further separated into two fractions by subjecting it to column chromatography. The first fraction (minor) was found to be a mixture of two biflavones (tlc of the methylated product), identified as monomethyl ethers of amentoflavone and cupressuflavone by comparison of Rf and shade in uv light with authentic samples. The second fraction crystallised from methanol as yellow cubes, m.p. 344°, gave a methyl ether ($\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4/\text{K}_2\text{CO}_3$), m.p. 262°, and an acetate ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$), m.p. 239°, was characterised as hinokiflavone by comparison of Rf, m.p. and pmr data with authentic samples¹¹. Fraction III crystallised from methanol as yellow cubes, m.p. 315°, on methylation and crystallisation ($\text{CHCl}_3 - \text{MeOH}$) yielded yellow needles, m.p. 262°. Acetylation ($\text{Ac}_2\text{O}/\text{Py}$) provided an acetate as yellow needles ($\text{CHCl}_3 - \text{MeOH}$), m.p. 214°. It was characterised as isocryptomerin by pmr spectral studies of its acetate and also by comparison of Rf, m.p. and shade in uv light with authentic samples¹¹.

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